

EMPLOYING INTERACTIVE APPROACHES IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12683283>

Annotation. This article deals with the information about specific techniques and methods that allow improving the use of interactive methods in the educational process in higher education institutions that can increase the effectiveness and quality of education, that is, making the lesson unusual and richer and more interesting. The author notes that the need for and focus on utilizing innovative, pedagogical, and information technologies in lessons is growing steadily within the educational process.

Key words: education, technology, interactive method, lesson, cognitive activity.

Today, in the field of education, modern pedagogical technologies, the experience of developed countries are widely used, the educational process is conducted on the basis of innovative approaches, multimedia tools, information and communication technologies are used rationally, and the process of education and exchange of experience at the international level is developing consistently. To improve the quality of education in higher education institutions, it is not enough for a teacher to have a deep knowledge of his specialty and impart a large amount of knowledge to an audience full of hungry young people. According to the results of many studies, a new approach to education, the use of active approaches in teaching students is one of the most effective ways of imparting knowledge.

In other words, students can easily perceive, understand and remember the given materials only when they are actively involved in the learning process. Based on this, the main methodological innovations require the use of interactive teaching methods. Especially in today's rapidly developing era, the most optimal way to increase the effectiveness of education is to organize training using interactive methods. According to the students' life position and professional self-determination, the professor teacher of each higher education institution asks how to organize the educational process in order to form an active attitude to learning and cognitive activities in students. In this regard, what methods and techniques or teaching technologies can have the most

effective effect? Pedagogical technologies are important in solving these problems in the educational process.

In the educational process, the demand and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the course of the lesson is increasing day by day [2]. One of the reasons for this is that, until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, but modern technologies allow them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, study and analyze it independently, and even draw conclusions by themselves. Active use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, improvement of educational efficiency, analysis and introduction into practice is one of the important tasks of today.

Teaching informatics with the help of interactive technologies allows to improve the cognitive activity of students, develop the ability to learn independently, develop teamwork skills, develop and form communication skills, and most importantly, increase educational motivation [1]. Interactive teaching allows students to actively participate in the learning process in order to get the most information and knowledge from their teachers, as well as use various methods of presentation of practical demonstrations and exercises. Teachers have a responsibility to encourage students to actively participate in classroom activities, apply their knowledge, and think for themselves in order to retain long-term memory [4]. In these ways, students' knowledge is improved, curiosity, energy, team spirit and freedom of speech are enhanced. Teachers encourage their students to accept tasks positively, perform them better, and produce positive and desirable results. The quality of a good teacher includes being observant, sensitive, agile, encouraging [5] and they should always work with an open mind so that they can motivate their students better and more effectively.

The methods of creating an opportunity for students to actively participate in the interactive learning process are given in the picture below.

Pic.1. Ways to create opportunities for active participation of students

The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal debates, the opportunity to describe and express the educational material freely, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is high, students' initiative, small group, are of particular importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. work in a group that has [3]. Learning strategies help the teaching method by making students actively participate in the learning process and learn in a different way, instead of being passive listeners of the lecture.

Thus, the organization of interactive education leads to simulation of life situations, general solution of issues based on the analysis of situations, penetration of the flow of information and its activity. It can be seen that the structure of an interactive lesson is different from the structure of a regular lesson. This requires professional skills and experience of the teacher. Therefore, the structure of the lesson includes only the elements of the interactive educational model - interactive technologies, that is, specific techniques and methods that make the lesson unusual and richer and more interesting.

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